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HOW DOES EER CONCEPTUALIZE ITS OBJECT OF STUDY? – AN EXPLORATION BASED ON THE “DIDAKTIK TRIANGLE”

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ABSTRACT

The Engineering Education Research (EER) community in Europe and across the globe has grown considerably in the past decades. There have been some examinations to date of the research corpus that has evolved, although these have been predominantly US-based. An emerging literature has started to chart the ways in which European EER-researchers have a distinctive tradition, which might at least in part be due to the influence of the European “Didaktik” tradition, which conceptualizes teaching and learning as fundamentally resting on an interplay between student, teacher, and the content (subject matter). This is represented in the “Didaktik triangle” where student, teacher, and the content are placed on the vertices of the triangle, and the sides of the triangle represent three important interrelations. This study compares the 50 most highly cited papers in each of the European Journal of Engineering Education (EJEE) and the US-based Journal of Engineering Education (JEE). Our analysis of how the topic(s) of the papers related to the “Didaktik triangle” shows that the conceptualization of the object of study in the EJEE papers was more related to the “Didaktik triangle” as a whole compared with papers published in JEE. The results of our study provide further evidence that there are, indeed, some differences in the aims of American and European EER. A global community would do well to try to draw on the strengths of both of these traditions.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 European Didaktik tradition

It has been suggested that educational thinking and research in continental and northern Europe is strongly influenced by the *Didaktik*² tradition [1, 2] with roots in the thinking of scholars like Johann Amos Comenius [3] and Johann Friedrich Herbart [4].

Didaktik can be defined as the science of teaching and learning. Künzli [5] summarizes the central questions of Didaktik into:

- What is to be taught and learned (i.e., the content aspect).
- How is “content” to be taught and learned? (i.e., the mediation or method aspect).
- Why is “content” to be taught and learned? (i.e., the goal aspect).

In the Didaktik tradition prominent emphases is given to content and goals – this means that the *what*- and the *why*-questions are indeed central considerations to be problematized and studied [2]. As succinctly expressed by Künzli [5] the “fundamental question of Didaktik is *Why is the student to learn the material in the first place?*” (italics in original). In the Anglo-Saxon curriculum-studies-tradition the *how*-question is seen as the core question while, typically, the content is more or less assumed as given and accordingly the *what*- and the *why*-questions are downplayed [2].

Borrego and Bernhard [6] offer one of the first studies in the literature that survey the EER field and contrast US and European approaches. They suggest that EER in Europe is mainly situated in the “Didaktik tradition” while EER in the US is more influenced by the “Curriculum-studies-tradition”. Thus, in Europe, deliberations regarding what should be learned and why it should be learned are seen as valid objects of study and are more in focus than in the US. Furthermore, they argue that in Europe EER research is to a higher degree problem-led (i.e. a focus on the problem investigated and the insights generated) while research in the US to a higher degree has been method-led (i.e. a focus on proper use of methodology and “rigorous” research).

Some further indication of how these differences in traditions play out in contemporary EER can be noted in the descriptions of the PhD-programmes in engineering education research at Purdue University, USA, and at Linköping University, Sweden, that both were initiated in 2004. According to Purdue’s description they “established ... engineering education doctoral program [in 2004], for students who wish to pursue rigorous research in *how* engineering is best taught, learned, and practiced” (our italics) while Linköping University presented the following description: “The subject of engineering education [Ingenjörsvetenskapens Didaktik] deals with learning, teaching and the formation of knowledge in the art and science of engineering in a broad sense. In focus stand fields of *knowledge of*

² The spelling, ‘Didaktik’ is deliberately used to distinguish the European ‘Didaktik tradition’ from the English term ‘didactics,’ which has a different meaning.

relevance for the practice of, and education for, the engineering profession and its relation to the advance of knowledge in techniques and technology. ...” [7, our translation]. Linköping University’s description also specifically mentions “selection of content” (ibid.) among other things. Thus, as demonstrated here a focus on the *what*, *how* and *why* can be seen in Linköping’s description, while a strong focus on the *how*-question and on “rigorous research” is prominent in Purdue’s description.

1.2 Didaktik triangle

A central tenet in the *Didaktik tradition* is that organized teaching should be seen as an active and dynamic triadic relationship (see Fig. 1) – the *Didaktik triangle* – between three elements: *Subject matter (content)*, *student*, and the *teacher* [e.g. 3, 4, 5].

Fig. 1. Didaktik triangle [5]

As can be seen in figure 1, *Teacher*, *Student* (learner), and *Content* (subject matter, object of learning) form the vertices of a triangle in this conceptualization of teaching and learning in a learning environment. The vertices are joined by the *Classroom intercourse axis* joining Teacher – Student, by the *Experience axis* joining Student – Content, and the *Representation axis* joining Content – Teacher. Within this model it is possible to lay different emphasis on different elements of the triangle or treat the elements in different ways. For example the Experience axis can be viewed in an “objective” way, i.e. in which ways the Student(s) is supposed to experience Content, or in a “subjective”, i.e. in which ways the Student(s) actually experience Content [5].

There exist many extensions to the Didaktik triangle. For example, Novak and Gowin [8] added Evaluation and Context (i.e. five vertices), Sträßler [9] added Artifacts used in teaching and learning and constructed a tetrahedron (i.e. four vertices), and Rezat and Sträßler [10] related the Didaktik triangle and the tetrahedron to Engeström’s elaborate activity system [11]. Kansanen and Meri [12] on the other hand argue for retaining the basic Didaktik triangle, but suggest that although the Didaktik triangle should be treated as a whole it is almost impossible to do so in practice. Thus, they claim, a productive approach to analysis is to focus on each pair (i.e. what are named axes above). The Teacher – Student pair (i.e. Classroom intercourse axis) he puts forward as the “pedagogical relation”. Furthermore, in his model, he added a “Didaktik relation” that is conceptualized as an arrow going from the Teacher affecting the Student – Content pair (i.e. Experience axis).

Fig. 2. a) Illustration of the “pedagogical relation” (to the left), and b) the “Didaktik relation” (to the right) according to Kansanen and Meri [12].

The Didaktik triangle can also be used to conceptualize aspects of the teaching and learning situation. Marton and co-workers [e.g. 13] distinguish between the *intended object of learning*, the *enacted object of learning* and the *lived object of learning*. The intended object of learning consists of the subject matter and the skills that the teacher or curriculum planner is expecting the students to learn and this would relate to the teachers view on Content, i.e. representation axis as indicated in fig. 3a. The enacted object is what it is actually made possible for the student to learn by the design of the learning environment and would correspond to the teachers enactment of the Representation and Classroom intercourse axes, while monitoring students’ experience as is indicated in fig. 3b. This mean that our view is slightly different from the view of Kansanen and Meri [12] presented in fig 2b. Finally, the lived object of learning is the way students see, understand, and make sense of the object of learning and the relevant capabilities that the students develop that would correspond to the Experience axis as indicated in fig. 3c.

Fig. 3. Conceptualization of a) intended, b) enacted, and c) lived object of learning [13] in relation to the Didaktik triangle

Although the model of the Didaktik triangle simplify what occurs within an engineering learning environment, in our view, it serves as a simple, but yet powerful enough, starting point to theorize the dynamics of teaching and learning, as well as contextualizing and situating the elements in relation to the each others. Thus, the aim of this study is investigate to what degree the elements of the Didaktik triangle can be identified in EER journal papers.

1.3 Previous investigations

Over the last period there has emerged a substantial literature looking at the theory and methods that are being used in EER. Much of this work has proceeded through bibliometric analyses of published articles, including investigations of author origins, citations, and the like (for example Williams, et al. [14] and Wankat, et al. [15]). But from early on there has also been deliberation in more detail on how EER researchers are approaching their research. Wankat [16] notes that while the JEE was starting to publish more articles with a research orientation, that there was still a very low level of use of educational theory in these. Koro-Ljungberg and Douglas [17] survey the emerging use of qualitative methodologies in EER and this is further expanded on by Case and Light [18]. Malmi, et al. [19] do a useful survey of EJEE articles to complement this literature which had hitherto tended to be quite US-focused. They show that while EJEE authors do show use of educational theory, this tends to be limited to a pretty narrow set of explanatory frameworks.

To our knowledge, the only investigation of EER using the Didaktik triangle as an analytical tool is the work by Kinnunen and Malmi [20]. They have investigated the papers presented in the EER-track at the SEFI annual conferences in 2010 and 2011. They further extended the Didaktik triangle of Kansanen and Meri [12] ending up with 13 categories and also applied a multi-layered Didaktik structure consisting of three layers; Teachers, Organization, and Society. Thus they ended up with 39 categories in their analysis making their results somewhat difficult to compare with the analysis we have done (See section 2 below). Furthermore they have only analysed a conference situated in Europe while we are comparing journals based in Europe and the US.

2 METHODOLOGY

Two of the leading scholarly journals in the field of EER are the Journal of Engineering Education (JEE) owned by American Society for Engineering Education (ASEE) and the European Journal of Engineering Education (EJEE) owned by European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI). Although both journals aim for an international readership and accept papers internationally we suggest that an analysis of publications in these journals can reveal differences in research traditions between the US and Europe as the authors published in EJEE are predominantly from Europe and the authors that get published in JEE are predominantly from the US.

In this study we used the Scopus database to retrieve the 50 most cited (according to Scopus) papers published between 2008 and May 2019 in JEE and EJEE respectively. The year 2008 was chosen as it was the year that SEFI's working group for Engineering Education Research was established. As in some instances citation rankings were shared, we ended up with 53 papers from EJEE and 51 papers from JEE.

In this study we aimed to develop an analytical tool based on the Didaktik triangle for analysing papers with some kind of empirical investigation of teaching and/or learning in university level engineering education. Papers that were out of scope for such an analysis – for example review papers, papers discussing the EER-field or methodology, or papers related to school level engineering education – were excluded from the analysis. Twelve papers were excluded for EJEE resulting in 41 papers being analysed, while for JEE 22 papers were excluded resulting in 29 papers being analysed.

3 RESULTS

In this preliminary analysis we used six non-exclusive categories related to the vertices and the axis of the Didaktik triangle. The characteristics that we used for assigning a paper to one or more of these categories is shown in the table below. For each category we refer to one paper that exemplifies this approach. For the first three categories, these are papers that we judged to have a predominant emphasis on one vertex of the triangle. The following three categories are papers where our analysis identifies a focus on one of the axes (the pairs). The final category refers to papers which we judged to represent all the dimensions of the triangle.

Table 1. Categories used in the analysis with examples of a paper classified to each category

Category	Characteristics of the category
Teacher	<p>The teacher(s) and some characteristics of the teacher(s) is/are apparently visible in the paper. <i>Example: Borrego, M., Froyd, J. E., & Hall, T. S. (2010). Diffusion of Engineering Education Innovations: A Survey of Awareness and Adoption Rates in U.S. Engineering Departments. Journal of Engineering Education, 99(3), 185-207.</i></p> <p>This study asked engineering department chairs in the US about their awareness of some common innovations in engineering education and to what extent any of these have been implemented in the department. The department chairs are seen, in this study, as being a representative for what is happening in the department. As this study is only focusing on the department chairs' awareness and his/her knowledge of teachers' adaption of innovative curricula within the department we categorise this paper in the <i>teacher</i> category.</p>
Student	<p>The student(s) and some characteristics of the student(s) is/are apparently visible in the paper. <i>Example: Marra, R. M., Rodgers, K. A., Shen, D., & Bogue, B. (2009). Women Engineering Students and Self-Efficacy: A Multi-Year, Multi-Institution Study of Women Engineering Student Self-Efficacy. Journal of Engineering Education, 98(1), 27-38.</i></p> <p>This study sought to characterize US women engineering students' self-efficacy (i.e. a person's belief in his/her own capabilities). As neither the relation to teachers nor content is explicitly discussed we categorise this paper in the <i>student</i> category.</p>
Content	<p>Content (Subject matter, object of learning) – i.e. the knowledge, values, and skills students are supposed to learn – is apparently visible in the paper. <i>Example: Male, S. A., Bush, M. B., & Chapman, E. S. (2011). An Australian study of generic competencies required by engineers. European Journal of Engineering Education, 36(2), 151-163.</i></p> <p>The views of established engineers on which generic competencies were seen as most important for engineering work have been studied. As this paper discusses the the knowledge and skills that are seen to important for the students to learn it is categorized as <i>content</i>.</p>

Table 1. Continued

Category	Characteristics of the category
Teacher–Student (Classroom intercourse axis)	<p>Some topic related to the Teacher–Student–relationship is apparent in the paper. Interactions with some proxy for the teacher, such as lab-instructions, are included in this category as these are designed by the teacher.</p> <p><i>Example: Vogt, C. M. (2008). Faculty as a Critical Juncture in Student Retention and Performance in Engineering Programs. Journal of Engineering Education, 97(1), 27-36.</i></p> <p>This paper addresses the importance of university teachers for the classroom climate and the development of students' self-efficacy, academic confidence, sound learning behaviours and performance. Thus the paper is categorized as related to the <i>teacher – student</i> relationship.</p>
Student–Content (Experience axis)	<p>Some topic related to the Student–Content–relationship is apparent in the paper. It could, for example, be how students have learned or experienced the content, but it could also be students' views on the content.</p> <p><i>Example: Daly, S. R., Yilmaz, S., Christian, J. L., Seifert, C. M., & Gonzalez, R. (2012). Design Heuristics in Engineering Concept Generation. Journal of Engineering Education, 101(4), 601-629.</i></p> <p>This paper presents a study of how engineering students and practitioners generated concepts and used a collection of design heuristics to explore design spaces. Thus <i>students'</i> (and practitioners) relation to content is explored in this paper.</p>
Content–Teacher (Representation axis)	<p>Some topic related to the Content–Teacher–relationship is apparent in the paper. It could, for example, be the teacher's view on content, but also how the teacher represents or selects content.</p> <p><i>Example: Ahern, A., O'Connor, T., McRuairc, G., McNamara, M., & O'Donnell, D. (2012). Critical thinking in the university curriculum – the impact on engineering education. European Journal of Engineering Education, 37(2), 125-132.</i></p> <p>This paper investigate how teachers in different disciplines define critical thinking and how they say they teach critical thinking in their courses. Thus the paper discuss how <i>teachers</i> think about <i>content</i>.</p>
All categories	<p><i>Example: Carstensen, A.-K., & Bernhard, J. (2009). Student learning in an electric circuit theory course: Critical aspects and task design. European Journal of Engineering Education, 34(4), 389-404.</i></p> <p>This study is an example of design-based research where the authors, in the context of an electric circuit theory course, deal with teachers' intended objects of learning, the enacted objects of learning through the design of tasks, and students' resulting lived object of learning. Thus all categories are explored in this paper.</p>

Figure 4. shows overall counts for the prevalence of the six categories across the papers that were analysed. A few conclusions are immediately apparent. Firstly, papers in both journals show a marked emphasis on considerations pertaining to the student. The EJEE papers show significantly more representation of matters relating to the teacher and to content, and also of the various 'pair' relations in the Didaktik triangle. These observations will be further unpacked in the section to follow.

4 DISCUSSION

This study is one of the first explorations using the Didaktik triangle as an analytical tool for investigating the topics in EER related to teaching and learning. This study demonstrates that this is a feasible method for analysing or conceptualizing EER, but

also as a potentially valuable model to be used in discussion about teaching and learning.

The results of this study further corroborates the suggestion by Borrego and Bernhard [6] that there are some differences between European and US research tradition, at least if the journals EJEE and JEE are taken as representatives for each tradition. Treatment of Content and the Teacher, and addressing the Didaktik triangle as a whole seem to be more predominant in EJEE. This is not a surprise as this corresponds to the differences seen in other areas of education [1, 2].

Fig. 4. Prevalence of the six different Didaktik triangle related categories in analysed papers.

The more frequent treatment of the Didaktik triangle as a whole can be taken as an indicator of more holistic thinking in Europe, but turned the other way around it could alternatively indicate that papers in EJEE are less focused than papers in JEE. Indeed Kansanen and Meri [12] pointed out that it in practice is very difficult to focus on the complete triangle. In our view being focused on one dimension of the triangle might well be a productive approach for research as long as one is aware of the fuller picture. A global EER-community would do well to understand and to try to draw on strengths of both traditions.

The Didaktik triangle can also be used in a more meta-level discussion to discuss if some topics are missing across the spectrum of EER literature. Fig. 4 shows that it is less common that EER address the Teacher or the Content vertices and it is less common to address the Teacher–Content pair. Indeed, Holmberg and Bernhard [21] used the Didaktik triangle to argue for the need to study teachers’ views on content.

In conclusion then, the findings of this preliminary study suggest that further engagement with the Didaktik triangle as an analytical approach, a theoretical model, and a spur for further conversations, could be a valuable addition to the global deliberations in the field of EER.

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